

Research Article

A Data-Driven Methodology for Quality Aware Code Fixing

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In today's rapidly changing software development landscape, ensuring code quality is essential to reliability, maintainability, and security among other aspects. Identifying code quality issues can be tackled; however, implementing code quality improvements can be a complex and time-consuming task. To address this problem, we present a novel methodology designed to assist developers by suggesting alternative code snippets that not only match the functionality of the original code but also improve its quality based on predefined metrics. Our system is based on a language-agnostic approach that allows the analysis of code snippets written in different programming languages. It employs advanced techniques to assess functional similarity and evaluates syntactic similarity, suggesting alternatives that minimize the need for extensive modification. The evaluation of our system on multiple axes demonstrates the effectiveness of our approach in providing usable code alternatives that are both functionally equivalent and syntactically similar to the original snippets, while significantly improving quality metrics. We argue that our methodology and tool can be valuable for the software engineering community, bridging the gap between the identification of code quality problems and the implementation of practical solutions that improve software quality.

Keywords: code fixing; code recommendations; data driven; software quality

1. Introduction

The importance of software engineering has grown significantly as a result of continuous technological advances and the widespread integration of software into every aspect of everyday life. As software is increasingly important for business processes, public services, and individual concerns, the demand for high-quality, maintainable, reliable, and efficient software is greater than ever. This highlights the need for robust software engineering methodologies that prioritize quality throughout the entire development process.

According to ISO/IEC 25010:2011 [1], quality for a piece of code or a software component is mainly related to eight quality attributes: *Functional Suitability*, *Usability*, *Maintainability*, *Portability*, *Reliability*, *Performance and Efficiency*, *Security*, and *Compatibility*.

The importance of software quality is highlighted by the significant amount of research being carried out on the subject. Current studies cover a wide range of aspects, from identifying

key quality characteristics and developing metrics to measure them [2–4], to exploring techniques for improving code quality through automated analysis and refactoring [5–9].

Despite the clear emphasis on software quality and the availability of standards such as ISO/IEC 25010, there remains a notable gap in the availability of tools capable of suggesting code fixes that improve the quality of software code. While there are many tools that identify potential quality issues, the development of systems that can automatically recommend corrective actions or improvements is still in its initial stages. This gap poses a significant challenge for developers who want to improve the quality of their code, but lack the guidance or tools to do so effectively. Approaches based on large language models (LLMs) have shown promise in generating code suggestions and improvements. However, these models often fall short in understanding the full context of the code, resulting in recommendations that may be syntactically correct but semantically incorrect or suboptimal. In addition, LLMs can struggle with complex, domain-specific logic and may not

always conform to best practices or the specific quality characteristics emphasized by standards such as ISO/IEC 25010. This highlights the need for more advanced, context-aware tools that can provide precise, actionable recommendations tailored to the specific needs and constraints of the code base.

In this study, we aim to fill this gap. Our main goal is to develop a system capable of providing developers with actionable recommendations, improving the quality of the code produced, and positively influencing the metrics associated with certain quality attributes. To achieve this, the system analyzes a piece of code submitted by the user, compares it with a collection of snippets with high-quality score, and suggests those that most closely match the desired functionality and meet the user's requirements.

The main contributions of our approach are as follows:

- **Development of a Quality-Aware Recommendation System:** We propose a system that analyzes user-submitted code snippets and recommends alternatives that fulfill the same functional requirements while demonstrating superior software quality characteristics and metrics.
- **Comprehensive Dataset Employment:** The system leverages a dataset [10] annotated with diverse software quality metrics, enabling thorough analysis and comparison of code snippets across multiple quality attributes.
- **Novel Functional Similarity Assessment Mechanism:** A mechanism is introduced to assess the functional similarity of code snippets, irrespective of their programming language, facilitating meaningful quality comparisons beyond syntax.
- **Syntactic Similarity Mechanism:** A syntactic similarity mechanism is included to recommend alternatives that require minimal changes to the original code, balancing ease of implementation with quality improvement.

Our goal with this research is to provide developers with specific, actionable recommendations that specifically target improvements in software quality attributes. By providing a system that not only identifies but also suggests functionally equivalent code snippets with optimized quality attributes, we aim to facilitate a significant improvement in the software development process. This approach aims to provide developers with a valuable tool to refine their code based on established quality metrics. To this end, we formulated three research questions, which are assessed in Section 4:

- **RQ1:** What are the key components of a quality-aware code-fixing system that can suggest functionally and/or syntactically similar snippets?
- **RQ2:** Does the proposed system effectively improve software quality metrics through its recommendations, thereby confirming the hypothesis that targeted code snippet replacements can enhance the overall quality attributes of software projects?
- **RQ3:** Given the advances and capabilities of LLMs in understanding and generating code, could an LLM effectively replace the proposed system by performing the

same tasks of identifying functionally similar code snippets and recommending alternatives with better quality metrics?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work in software quality evaluation, metrics, recommendation systems, and LLMs, highlighting the gaps addressed by our study. Section 3 details the proposed methodology, including data processing, similarity assessment, and clustering techniques. Section 4 presents the results, demonstrating the system's ability to suggest high-quality code alternatives. Section 5 concludes with a summary of contributions and potential directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

Literature on software engineering methodologies, techniques for improving code quality, and recommendation systems for enhancing software quality is extensive and diverse. Relevant research highlights the dynamic nature of software development and the crucial importance of quality in maintaining the functionality and reliability of software systems. This section provides an overview of relevant studies in these areas, establishing a basis for our research and identifying issues that our study aims to address.

The ability to quantify software quality and its characteristics has constituted a significant area of research within the field. A plethora of studies have focused on developing metrics and models that can effectively assess various aspects of software quality. For instance, our previous work [11] discusses the development of automated tools for analyzing code quality, with a particular focus on the aspect of code readability. Quantifying software quality relies on the adoption of diverse metrics and models, which are employed to assess the various quality attributes of software systems. These metrics are fundamental to the comprehension and enhancement of software product quality. Researchers have investigated a range of approaches to quantify software quality. These include the use of software coupling and cohesion models [12], design-time quality attributes and metrics [13], and multi-criteria decision-making approaches [14, 15]. These methods facilitate the analysis and evaluation of software quality based on factors such as usability, testability, and reusability.

Research on improving code quality has led to the development of various methods aimed at enhancing maintainability, readability, and overall software robustness. One significant approach involves identifying and refactoring non-maintainable packages, which helps prevent maintenance issues and promotes better code practices [3]. Additionally, automated refactoring techniques [16] focus on detecting code smells and suggesting specific refactoring actions to improve code structure and readability. Other studies have focused on addressing specific code smells through targeted refactorings. For example, an automated extract method refactoring approach has been proposed to correct the long method smell, enhancing readability and modularity by decomposing large, monolithic methods into smaller, more manageable ones [17]. Similarly, targeted recommendations such as extracting complex expressions into local variables have been explored to improve maintainability and reduce

cognitive load for developers [18]. Machine learning models have also been employed to predict and recommend code quality improvements, leveraging large datasets of annotated code snippets to provide data-driven suggestions for enhancing software projects [2]. Beyond traditional rule-based refactoring, reinforcement learning has also been applied to automate software restructuring. A DQN-based agent has been introduced to learn effective refactoring sequences through exploration and feedback, demonstrating improvements in software quality metrics [19]. Real-time feedback mechanisms have also been explored to aid developers in maintaining code quality. The Live Refactoring Environment provides immediate, visually driven suggestions during coding, enabling developers to address potential issues proactively and enhance software maintainability [20]. However, traditional metrics often fall short when addressing the nuanced requirements of specialized domains. Jin et al. [21] proposed a distribution-based method for evaluating quality metrics, addressing inconsistencies and limitations in traditional measures. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of metrics depends on their ability to adapt to both general-purpose programming and domain-specific requirements.

Recommendation Systems in Software Engineering (RSSEs) are designed to provide valuable information tailored to specific software engineering tasks within a given context. These systems address the challenge of meeting developers needs and preferences by offering tailored suggestions. By helping developers cope with the huge amount of information in modern software projects, RSSEs play a crucial role in enhancing software quality and streamlining the development process [22]. RSSEs assist developers by enabling navigation through diverse sources of information, whether within the context of a given project or online, and suggesting items that are relevant to the task [23]. AI-driven tools are also being integrated into the code review process. AICodeReview, for instance, leverages automated heuristics and historical feedback to suggest improvements during peer reviews, thereby promoting higher code quality standards [24].

The integration of RSSEs aims to assist software engineers in developing systems efficiently, particularly through the use of existing APIs and model-based systems engineering practices [25, 26]. These systems are vital in enhancing the efficiency and quality of software development by providing developers with high-quality, contextually relevant recommendations.

Recent studies have highlighted the limitations of existing code recommendation systems and quality metrics. Liu et al. [27] evaluated large pretrained language models for recommending code updates, identifying challenges in handling complex and specialized codebases. Similarly, Silavong et al. [28] proposed “Senatus,” a fast and accurate recommendation engine designed to address scalability issues in large, diverse codebases. These studies underline the need for systems that can adapt to varied and complex programming contexts.

Piyadasa et al. [29] provided an extensive review of recent advancements in recommended systems, identifying key challenges such as handling complex data and specialized domains. Kumar et al. [30] further explored trends in recommender systems, emphasizing scalability and data sparsity challenges

that limit their application to highly specialized coding scenarios.

Recently, the evolution of LLMs such as GPT has brought new possibilities for assisting in software development tasks, including code snippet generation. One may argue that their capabilities could be employed to provide a novel way to improve software quality by suggesting code improvements and alternatives that conform to best practices and are optimized for performance, readability, and maintainability. Even, the use of LLMs to generate code snippets could potentially optimize the development process, reduce the incidence of errors, and improve the overall quality of software projects by providing developers with high quality, contextually relevant code suggestions. Newer approaches like CodeQUEST adopt an iterative method using GPT-4o to assess and enhance code quality across multiple dimensions, including maintainability and security. Their results indicate that structured, iterative prompting can lead to measurable quality improvements [31].

However, recent studies reveal limitations in the direct application of LLMs in improving software quality. Research suggests that while LLMs, such as GPT, can produce functionally accurate and syntactically correct code, their effectiveness in addressing complex software quality metrics is not as impactful as initially anticipated. Studies indicate that code generated by LLMs may not consistently adhere to best coding practices, potentially introducing complexity or security vulnerabilities rather than mitigating them [32–34]. In addition, the current capabilities of LLMs appear insufficient to apply advanced software engineering principles, such as code refactoring for readability or performance optimization [35, 36]. This gap highlights a fundamental challenge: LLMs’ code generation capabilities do not lead to software quality improvement, highlighting the need to rather integrate LLMs with established software engineering practices for quality improvement.

Taking these findings into account, our approach is to use LLMs not as a stand-alone tool, but as part of a more comprehensive strategy to improve the quality of software. By merging the capabilities of LLMs with robust software quality engineering methodologies, we aim to build a system that provides actionable recommendations for code improvement. This hybrid approach seeks to exploit the best of both “worlds,” utilizing the generative strengths of LLMs while addressing their limitations through targeted software quality analytics.

By integrating various methodologies, our research aims to bridge the existing gaps in software quality improvement. The hybrid approach we propose combines the generative strengths of LLMs with well-established software engineering practices. This enables the development of a robust recommendation system that provides precise, actionable suggestions for enhancing code quality. Our system offers practical solutions, thereby facilitating the continuous improvement of software projects.

In conclusion, the literature highlights the importance of maintaining high software quality and the potential of recommendation systems in achieving this goal. While significant progress has been made in both evaluating and improving software quality, the integration of LLMs with traditional

FIGURE 1: The architecture of our approach.

software engineering techniques offers a promising area for further research. Our study aims to fill this gap by developing a system that provides developers with specific, actionable suggestions for improving the quality of their code, thereby positively impacting the metrics of key quality attributes.

3. Materials and Methods

In this section, we present the methodology we have developed for improving software quality in the form of actionable recommendations (illustrated in Figure 1). It incorporates two core components: a functional similarity and a syntactic similarity calculator. These components work collaboratively to evaluate code snippets against extensive datasets, providing recommendations that not only match the intended functionality but also adhere to specific quality characteristics. Our methodology employs a thorough process that begins with the preprocessing of datasets, followed by the implementation of clustering techniques and modifications to optimize the performance and accuracy of code snippets, as well as the application of a quality model, in order to identify the quality degree of each code snippet. The result is a set of recommendations that are functionally and syntactically aligned with the user's original code, promising ease of implementation and improved quality. The following subsections describe all the components that comprise our recommendation system.

3.1. Datasets. In the development of our recommendation system, a crucial step is the establishment of a solid dataset that serves as the basis for the generation of high-quality code recommendations. This dataset should consist of a diverse pool of code snippets to ensure the functionality of our system. It is important to note that the dataset used in this paper is only for demonstration purposes; the inherent flexibility of our system allows for the seamless integration of any code snippet library, thus extending the applicability and usefulness of our approach to different contexts and requirements.

Also, it should be noted that our methodology is language-agnostic, meaning it can handle code snippets in any programming language as long as the dataset contains snippets in the

same language as the user's input. This feature enhances the flexibility of our system, making it an invaluable tool for developers working with a wide range of programming languages.

To create a comprehensive dataset, we combined code snippets from three different sources: the code snippets dataset, the code modifications dataset, and the code idioms dataset. This was done to ensure a diverse range of code snippets for analysis, which would improve the potential for our system to provide relevant recommendations.

It is important to note that each code snippet in our dataset has been carefully annotated with quality metrics before being included. These metrics provide a quantitative basis for evaluating the quality of code snippets, making it easier to recommend alternatives that not only meet the desired functionality but also excel in specific quality attributes. We discuss the calculation of quality metrics in Subsection 3.2.

3.1.1. Code Snippets Dataset. In the methodology of our study, significant emphasis is placed on the utilization of a rich dataset of code snippets that forms the basis of the recommendations made by our system. In the dataset crafted in our previous work [10], we have included a large number of code snippets, originally derived from the CodeSearchNet corpus [37], along with not only the functional aspects of code snippets but also a plethora of quality metrics. The dataset originates from the CodeSearchNet corpus, which provides a diverse range of code snippets from various programming languages.

To address the important aspects of software quality, specifically maintainability and readability, we have enriched the dataset with additional information. This includes static analysis metrics, code violations, and readability assessments. This augmentation enables a comprehensive evaluation of code snippets, ensuring that the recommendations not only meet the functional requirements, but also adhere to high standards of code quality.

Table 1 depicts some statistics about the collected dataset, as they were originally presented in [10].

3.1.2. Code Modifications Dataset. Our research on improving software quality benefits from an alternative dataset that

TABLE 1: Code snippets dataset statistics.

Metric	Value
Number of Documents/Snippets	496,685
Average Snippets LOC	17.8
Number of Repositories	500
Data Size	11.3 GB

TABLE 2: Code modifications dataset statistics.

Metric	Value
Number of Modifications/Snippets	532
Number of Final Clusters	13
Average Silhouette Score	0.83

```

try {
    writer.close ();
}
catch (IOException e) {
    throw new Exception (e);
}
(a)

```

```

try {
    $ (object).close ();
}
catch (IOException e) {
    throw new $ (method) (e);
}
(b)

```

FIGURE 2: (a) An example idiom extracted by our system. (b) Generalized form of the pattern adding metavariables.

focuses on specific code changes. The dataset we have developed in our previous work [38] focuses on the evolution of code through distinct modifications, providing an additional perspective for assessing their impact on software quality metrics. We meticulously gathered and analyzed code changes from well-known GitHub projects and categorized them into separate modifications.

Each entry in this dataset contains a before and after snapshot of code, along with calculated quality metrics to show the impact of the modifications. This comparison provides a comprehensive view of how changes, from minor adjustments to major structural alterations, affect quality metrics. Additionally, our dataset clusters modifications based on their impact on quality metrics. This approach enables a structured exploration of code modifications by grouping those with similar effects on software quality. The clustering simplifies the analysis and reveals patterns and trends within the large number of code changes, offering practical insights for enhancing software quality.

The integration of this dataset into our recommendation system is important, since it enables the system to provide targeted suggestions for quality improvement. The system analyzes a user's code snippet against the curated dataset to identify modifications that have a history of enhancing similar quality metrics. This process ensures that the recommendations are functionally aligned and tailored to the developer's priorities, with the aim of improving the software quality attributes.

Table 2 depicts some statistics about the collected and processed modifications collected in [38].

3.1.3. Code Idioms Dataset. Building upon our previous work [8], the Code Idioms dataset serves as a valuable resource for developers by providing high-quality, syntactically and semantically robust code snippets. These idioms adhere to coding best practices, ensuring maintainability and robustness in software development. The dataset is particularly useful in enabling developers to quickly integrate well-established coding patterns into their projects, thereby enhancing functional suitability and reducing development effort.

TABLE 3: Number of idioms extracted per category.

Type of CFS Blocks	Number of Idioms
If	44
For	20
Enhanced For	15
Try	15
While	5
Switch	1
Do	1

Figure 2 illustrates an example idiom extracted using our approach, alongside its generalized form, showcasing the transformation into a reusable pattern. Table 3 shows the distribution of these idioms across different control flow statement (CFS) categories.

3.2. Quality Model—Software Quality Metrics. Following the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard [1], we recognize the complex nature of software quality, which breaks down into subcharacteristics that include functional suitability, usability, maintainability, portability, reliability, performance and efficiency, security, and compatibility. These quality dimensions, which have been thoroughly detailed in prior works, establish a framework for our analysis.

Static analysis and computational metrics are essential in evaluating software quality. For example, metrics such as Halstead's calculated program length (HCPL), McCabe's cyclomatic complexity (McCC), and weighted methods per class (WMC) are used to measure software complexity. These metrics provide insight into the software's structural complexity and its impact on maintainability and reliability. When evaluating the interaction between software components, it is important to consider coupling metrics such as coupling between object classes (CBO), Number of Incoming Invocations (NII), and number of outgoing invocations (NOI). These metrics reveal the interdependencies that affect performance efficiency and maintainability. Metrics that focus on documentation, such as comment density (CD) and documentation lines

TABLE 4: The calculated metrics per source code property.

Property	Name	Static Analysis Metrics	
		Description	Method
Complexity	HCPL	Halstead Calculated Program Length	↘
	HDIF	Halstead Difficulty	↘
	HEFF	Halstead Effort	↘
	HPL	Halstead Program Length	↘
	HPV	Halstead Program Vocabulary	↘
	HTRP	Halstead Time Required to Program	↘
	HVOL	Halstead Volume	↘
	MI	Maintainability Index	↗
	McCC	McCabe's Cyclomatic Complexity	↘
	NL	Nesting Level	↘
	NLE	Nesting Level Else-If	↘
WMC	Weighted Methods per Class	—	
Coupling	CBO	Coupling Between Object classes	↘
	CBOI	CBO Inverse	↘
	NII	Number of Incoming Invocations	↘
	NOI	Number of Outgoing Invocations	↘
	RFC	Response set For Class	—
Documentation	AD	API Documentation	↗
	CD	Comment Density	↗
	CLOC	Comment Lines of Code	↗
	DLOC	Documentation Lines of Code	↗
Size	LLOC	Logical Lines of Code	↘
	LOC	Lines of Code	↘

of code (DLOC), provide insight into the comprehensibility of the codebase, which directly impacts its usability and ease of maintenance. In addition, metrics such as logical lines of code (LLOC) and lines of code (LOC) provide insight into the size of the software, which is crucial for assessing its adaptability and efficiency in different environments. Dimaridou et al. [39] detail the relationship between these metrics and the quality attributes they represent. Applying these metrics across different software aspects offers a comprehensive assessment of quality, encompassing the code's internal characteristics and their broader effects on product quality [3].

Our methodology uses a range of metrics based on static analysis to measure different aspects of software quality. These metrics are essential for our analysis and cover various domains:

- **Complexity metrics**, such as HCPL and McCC, evaluate software complexity, highlighting potential challenges in maintenance or understanding.
- **Coupling metrics**: Measures such as CBO evaluate the interdependencies within the software, which can affect its maintainability and efficiency.
- **Documentation Metrics**, such as CD and DLOC, shed light on the comprehensiveness of the code documentation, which can influence usability and maintainability.
- **Size Metrics**, such as LLOC and LOC, provide insights into the scale of the software, which is crucial for evaluating its portability and efficiency.

Table 4 outlines the metrics utilized in our analysis, categorized by their impact on software quality. Positive changes in some metrics, indicated by an upward arrow, contribute positively to improved quality, whereas positive changes in other metrics, marked by a downward arrow, indicate a decrease in overall quality. A dash signifies metrics not applicable at a certain computational level. This table was originally presented in our previous work [38].

SourceMeter¹, a tool for analyzing source code, was used to calculate metrics from source code files in our collection. Calculating these metrics forms the foundation of our recommendation system, ensuring that proposed code alternatives are consistent with the desired improvements in software quality.

3.3. Functional Similarity Calculation. The functional similarity calculation subsystem is the core of our system, uniquely identifying the operational similarity between two snippets of code. This approach delves into the essence of what operations the code performs, offering an advanced perspective that is inherently language-agnostic, unlike conventional comparisons that focus on syntax. This feature is crucial as it highlights our system's capacity to assess code snippets in various programming languages based on their functionality. Figure 3 illustrates the mechanism for calculating the functional similarity between two snippets of code.

The evaluation process starts with using GPT-4's assistants feature to analyze and summarize code snippets in terms of

FIGURE 3: The functional similarity calculation algorithm.

```

if (book != null && borrowedBooks.contains (book)) {
    borrowedBooks.remove (book);
    book.returnBook ();
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 1: The first snippet of the functional similarity calculation example.

their functionality. We have created a specialized GPT assistant for this purpose. This initial step transforms the code into a summary of actions represented as tags. The assistant generates these tags by decomposing the functional intent behind the code, providing a basic level of comparison.

After obtaining the action tags from GPT-4, we process them using natural language processing (NLP) techniques. We use the Python NLTK library² to perform a series of preprocessing steps, including normalization (handling casing differences), synonym resolution, stemming, lemmatization, and the elimination of stop words. These steps streamline and standardize the tags for accurate comparison.

To compare the processed tags, we employed Google's Universal Sentence Encoder [40] to evaluate semantic similarity, using the implementation included in the spaCy package³. This is quantified by a similarity score, with a score above a predefined threshold indicating functional equivalence between tags. The threshold was established through extensive experimentation to ensure reliability. The final similarity score between two code snippets is calculated as follows:

Let T_1 and T_2 be the sets of processed tags for snippet 1 and snippet 2, respectively. The similarity score, S , is determined by the equation:

$$S = \frac{T_1 \cap T_2}{T_1 \cup T_2} \quad (1)$$

This equation represents the intersection of tags over their union, providing a percentage score that reflects how functionally similar the two snippets are. To illustrate the functionality and effectiveness of our functional similarity calculation subsystem more clearly, let us examine a practical example. We will compare two code snippets that, despite originating from different contexts, perform quite similar operations. This comparison will demonstrate how our system goes beyond

syntactical differences to uncover the underlying functional similarities between code snippets.

Consider the first snippet depicted in **Code Snippet 1**. This snippet checks if a book is included in a list of borrowed books and, if so, removes it from the list and calls a method to mark it as returned.

In contrast, we encounter a second snippet in an entirely different context, achieving the same functionality but with a different syntax, as depicted in **Code Snippet 2**.

Table 5 depicts the list of tags derived from GPT-4 assistants for the two snippets, as well as the same list after the preprocessing step with NLTK has been applied. From the final lists of tags, using the Universal Sentence Encoder, we can conclude that the four tags of snippet 1 match with the latest four tags of snippet 2. Thus, the intersection of the tags of the two snippets is 4, while the union of the two sets is 5, resulting in a similarity score of 80%.

This example illustrates our system's capability to identify and measure functional similarities among code snippets, beyond mere textual or syntactic comparisons. By analyzing the core purpose of the code, our system effectively identifies snippets that have a common functional purpose, despite differences in implementation details. This process is based on NLP techniques and semantic analysis. It enhances the language-agnostic nature of the system and its potential to guide developers toward functionally equivalent, quality-enhancing code alternatives.

3.4. Clustering. Clustering is a crucial preprocessing step in our system. It simplifies the process of comparing the user's code snippet with the database of code snippets. By organizing snippets into groups based on functional similarity, we aim to reduce the computational load. Initially, we compare the user's snippet only with the centroid of each cluster. This approach enables us to identify the cluster that is most similar to the

```

switch (item)
{
case null:
break;
default:
if (listedItems.Contains (item))
{
listedItems.Remove (item);
item.ReturnItem();
}
break;
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 2: The second snippet of the functional similarity calculation example.

TABLE 5: Functional similarity steps.

Metric	Value
Tags for Snippet 1	['Checking if an object is not null', 'Checking if an object exists in a collection', 'Removing an object from a collection', 'Calling an object method']
Tags for Snippet 2	['Switch statement', 'Null checking', 'Checking if an item is in a list', 'Removing an item from a list', 'Invoking a method on an object']
Processed Tags for Snippet 1	['check object null', 'check object exist collect', 'remov object collect', 'call object method']
Processed Tags for Snippet 2	['switch statement', 'null check', 'check item list', 'remov item list', 'invok method object']
Intersection of Tags Length	4
Union of Tags Length	5
Similarity Score S	$\frac{4}{5} = 80\%$

user's input, allowing for a more focused comparison within that cluster.

To categorize the code snippets effectively, we first created a distance matrix that reflects the functional dissimilarity between pairs of snippets. The distance formula D used is a direct reflection of functional similarity S , which we define as

$$D(\text{snippet1}, \text{snippet2}) = 1 - S(\text{snippet1}, \text{snippet2}) \quad (2)$$

For the clustering, we employed the K -means algorithm for its simplicity and proven efficiency. K -means groups data into k distinct clusters by minimizing the distance between data points and the centroid of their assigned cluster. In this context, we processed the functional similarity scores between code snippets to drive the clustering, allowing the algorithm to organize the snippets based on common functional characteristics.

To determine the ideal number of clusters, we performed an analysis by varying the number of clusters and assessing the

effectiveness of each model using the silhouette score. The silhouette score is a measure of how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters. The equations below illustrate the calculation of the mean intra-cluster distance

$$a(i) = \frac{1}{|C_i| - 1} \sum_{\substack{j \in C_i \\ j \neq i}} d(i, j), \quad (3)$$

and the mean nearest-cluster distance

$$b(i) = \min_{k \neq i} \frac{1}{|C_k|} \sum_{j \in C_k} d(i, j), \quad (4)$$

leading to the silhouette score

$$s(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max(a(i), b(i))} \quad (5)$$

The calculations identified a clustering configuration that partitions the snippets optimally, ensuring meaningful grouping based on functional similarities. The silhouette score serves as a reliable metric for evaluating the coherence and distinction of the formed clusters, ensuring that each cluster accurately represents a distinct functional grouping within our dataset.

Through this clustering process, we greatly improve the efficiency and accuracy of our recommendation system. This allows it to quickly identify functionally equivalent code snippets that not only meet the user's functional requirements but also suggest improvements in software quality.

3.5. Recommendations Based on Functional Similarity. The recommendation system suggests code alternatives based on functional similarity, tailored to the user's desire to enhance specific quality metrics of their code. This section explains the pipeline through which user code snippets undergo analysis, comparison, and ultimately receive recommendations for improvement.

When a user submits a code snippet, the system compares it to pre-established clusters using the functional similarity algorithm described in Subsection 3.3. These clusters represent distinct functionalities that have been identified through a thorough analysis as described in Subsection 3.4 and extracted from our dataset. The comparison with centroids acts as a preliminary filter to identify clusters that closely match the functionality of the user's snippet, that way significantly reducing the computational needs.

After identifying the most similar clusters, the system proceeds to a more detailed comparison. During this stage, the user's snippet is carefully compared to each member of the selected clusters. This comparison is based again on the functional similarity algorithm, ensuring a focused analysis within a relevant functional context and improving the precision of our recommendations.

The recommendation process integrates the user's quality improvement objectives. The system tailors its recommendations to align with the desired quality outcomes, depending on the dataset used. This can be either the code snippets dataset for direct quality metric comparison or the code modifications dataset for assessing impact on quality metrics.

- **Code Snippets Dataset:** the system compares the quality metrics of the user's snippet against those of the snippets within the most similar clusters. Based on this comparison, snippets that exhibit superior quality metrics, aligned with the user's goals (e.g., improved complexity metrics), are highlighted as potential recommendations.
- **Code Modifications Dataset:** the analysis aims to determine the previous quality impact of the snippets within the selected clusters. By tracing back to the quality-impact clusters to which these snippets belong, the system can determine whether they have previously tended to improve the targeted quality metrics.

It is important to recognize that software quality metrics are interdependent and often present a complex trade-off scenario, where improving some metrics may have a negative

impact on others. Therefore, when considering snippet replacements, it is important to examine various alternatives in order to select the one(s) that best meet the developer's quality-related needs.

3.6. Syntactic Similarity Calculation. An additional, optional step in our recommendation system is the evaluation of syntactic similarity. This step aims to ensure that the suggestions provided not only offer improvements in code quality but are also syntactically similar to the user's original snippet. By focusing on syntactic similarity, we minimize the effort required for the developer to integrate the recommended snippet, allowing for a smoother transition and fewer changes.

For syntactic comparison, we use the abstract syntax tree (AST) representations of the code snippets. By analyzing these ASTs, we compute the tree edit distance (TED), which quantifies the minimum sequence of node edits (insertions, deletions, and label changes) required to transform one tree into another [41]. Despite the fundamental role of TED in assessing syntactic similarity, its computational complexity, typically at least $O(n^2)$, poses a challenge for efficiency.

To navigate this complexity efficiently, we utilize the pq-Grams algorithm [42] as an approximation for TED, as we have already used before in [8]. This method first requires transforming the AST into an ordered label tree T , using AST statement types as labels and structuring the tree for pre-order traversal. The pq -Grams technique extends T into a pq -Extended-Tree T^{pq} by incorporating null nodes to achieve a consistent structure for comparison.

The transformation into a pq -Extended-Tree involves adding $p - 1$ ancestor nodes to the tree's root and $q - 1$ (and q for leaves) child nodes to non-leaf nodes, ensuring a complete traversal pattern. For our methodology, we opt for $p = 2$ and $q = 3$, aligning with values that have historically yielded effective results in tree matching. Figure 4 illustrates this transformation process for a simple labeled tree, as it was originally presented in [43].

Each pq -Extended-Tree is then transformed into pq -Gram patterns, defining the *Profiles* $P(T)$ of the tree. These profiles encapsulate the structural essence of the AST, enabling a comparative analysis of syntactic structures. The syntactic similarity between two code snippets is determined by comparing the pq -Gram profiles of their respective ASTs, employing the formula below to calculate pq -Gram distance D :

$$D(T_1, T_2) = 1 - 2 * \frac{|P^{p,q}(T_1) \cap P^{p,q}(T_2)|}{|P^{p,q}(T_1) \cup P^{p,q}(T_2)|} \quad (6)$$

This equation quantifies the syntactic distance based on the overlap of pq -Gram patterns between two trees, providing a distance score that ranges from 0 (identical) to 1 (no similarity). It is obvious that the similarity between two trees can be easily calculated using the formula $1 - D(T_1, T_2)$. The final similarity value ranges from 0 to 1.

By integrating syntactic similarity assessment into our recommendation pipeline, we enable developers to not only improve the quality of their code, but to do so with minimal syntactic deviation from their original code. This additional

FIGURE 4: (a) Example tree T . (b) $T^{2,3}$ Extended-Tree.

layer of comparison enhances the utility and applicability of our system, making the adoption of recommended code snippets more seamless and less disruptive.

3.7. Final Recommendations. The final stage of our recommendation system delivers carefully selected code suggestions that are both functionally appropriate and syntactically similar to the user's original snippet. This process is designed to ensure that the recommendations not only improve specific quality metrics but also closely match the existing code, reducing the effort required for integration.

First, the system identifies snippets from the dataset that are functionally similar to the user's input and have potential for quality improvement. It then evaluates these snippets for syntactic similarity, using the pq -Grams algorithm to assess their structural similarity to the user's code. This twofold analysis allows for a balanced selection of recommendations that are likely to improve code quality with minimal modification effort.

The recommendations aim to find a balance between improving code quality and minimizing the development effort required to incorporate new code snippets. This balance is crucial for practical software development, where the cost of integrating new code is a significant consideration.

For example, if a user wants to improve the maintainability of their code, the system first identifies functionally related snippets that have superior maintainability metrics. Among these candidates, it then prioritizes those with high syntactic similarity to the user's code, ensuring that the recommendations are both useful and easy to adopt.

4. Results

To validate the effectiveness and practical applicability of our recommendation system, we designed our evaluation carefully around a number of scenarios. Each scenario is designed to highlight different aspects of the system's performance, providing a comprehensive view of its ability to improve software development practices.

The initial scenario focuses on the fundamental aspect of our architecture, the key components of our system. It includes the evaluation of the functional similarity calculation function, as well as the practical applicability of the proposed architecture in real-world applications, in order to establish a baseline for the overall effectiveness of the system in identifying

functionally and/or syntactically equivalent code snippets of improved quality.

The next scenario focuses on the system's core task of improving software quality metrics. This evaluation aspect examines the system's ability to recommend code changes that specifically improve desired quality attributes. By analyzing the outcomes of these recommendations, we evaluate the system's effectiveness in increasing the quality standards of software products, thus meeting its expectations as a software quality improvement tool.

Finally, we included an evaluation scenario to assess whether LLMs could effectively replace our system. Given the advances and capabilities of LLMs in understanding and generating code, we compared our approach with three prominent LLMs: Llama 3, Claude 3 Sonnet, and GPT-4o. We evaluated these models along three axes: syntactic correctness, functional similarity, and quality of proposed snippets. The aim of this comparison was to determine whether LLMs could match or exceed the performance of our system in identifying functionally similar code snippets and recommending high-quality alternatives.

The evaluation of our system on these scenarios aims to validate the strengths of our system, underlying its novelty and added value.

4.1. System Evaluation. The main aim of this evaluation is to assess the subsystems that comprise the proposed system and its key components. This assessment includes three different evaluation scenarios: the evaluation of the functional similarity calculation algorithm, the assessment of the effectiveness of the recommendation system in real-world applications, and the evaluation of the practical applicability of our system using the Code Idioms dataset.

4.1.1. Functional Similarity Evaluation. In order to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of our functional similarity component, we enlisted experienced developers (with at least 5 years of experience in software engineering), in a comparative analysis of code snippets. The aim of this direct involvement was to compare human judgment of functional similarity with the assessments generated by our automated function. We argue that this validates the effectiveness and precision of our system.

To achieve this, we built a web application to aid in this assessment⁴. The interface guides participants through a structured process to collect their ratings of the functional similarity

FIGURE 5: The first page of the functional similarity evaluation page.

between pairs of code snippets. The evaluation process is divided into three key screens, each serving a distinct purpose in the study.

Figure 5 illustrates the initial screen of our platform, which provides participants with clear instructions on the task of assessing functional similarity between code snippets. This step ensures that users understand the evaluation criteria and how their input contributes to the study.

Figure 6 depicts the second screen, which collects basic information about the participants, including their optional email address and their level of expertise in four programming languages: *Java*, *JavaScript*, *Python*, and *C++*. This data collection is intended to validate the language-agnostic nature of our approach and customize the evaluation experience to the participant's areas of expertise.

In the final phase, participants are presented with couples of code snippets, as shown in Figure 7. The evaluators are requested to grade the functional similarity of the snippets on a scale from 0% (no similarity) to 100% (identical functionality). The interface enables users to skip and move on to a new pair of snippets if they encounter any uncertainties.

The evaluation platform was populated with a diverse and rich set of code snippets using the CodeSearchNet corpus [37], which provides a rich collection of code snippets across multiple programming languages. To minimize the occurrence of pairs with 0% similarity and exclude overly complex snippets, we preprocessed the snippets using our functional similarity function, given the extensive diversity of the corpus. The aim of this initial filtering was to present participants with significant comparisons while avoiding both simplistic and excessively complicated scenarios.

We evaluated our approach across four programming languages. We aligned the snippet pairs with each participant's reported expertise to ensure that the assessment was based on the participant's area of knowledge, enhancing the validity of their responses. Thus, each participant was shown sets of code snippets only in the programming languages with which they were familiar. The frequency of each programming language used was based on their level of expertise. For instance, if the user has an expertise level of 3 (highest) in Java and level 1 (lowest) in C++, the system will display Java snippets three times more frequently than C++ snippets, while snippets in Python or JavaScript will not be displayed.

The users evaluated 335 different pairs of code snippets in total and submitted their functional similarity. Figure 8 illustrates the distribution of the pairs of code snippets into the four programming languages used in the evaluation scenario. The balanced distribution of code snippet pairs across the four programming languages underscores the versatility of our approach in handling different programming contexts.

Figure 9 presents a comparative analysis of the functional similarity scores as assessed by our methodology and by the participants. Subfigure 9a shows a histogram of the scores generated by our system, while Subfigure 9b shows the distribution of the scores as rated by the participants of our evaluation scenario. The similarity of the distributions between these two perspectives is a positive indicator, suggesting a good match between the automated scores and the intuitive judgments of experienced developers. This agreement validates the effectiveness of our methodology in accurately capturing functional similarities.

Functional Similarity Evaluation

User Details

Email (optional):

Programming Languages Level 1 (Taught at university/course):

JavaScript Java C++ Python Other

Programming Languages Level 2 (Used in personal projects):

JavaScript Java C++ Python Other

Programming Languages Level 3 (Used in professional environment):

JavaScript Java C++ Python Other

FIGURE 6: The second page of the functional similarity evaluation page.

Functional Similarity Evaluation

Progress: 1 / 20

Snippet 1

```

1 private <T> String convertToRawListString(Collection<T> collection) {
2     return "[" + collection.stream().map(x -> ""+x.toString()+"").collect(Coll
3 }

```

Snippet 2

```

1 public static Result badRequest(Path content, boolean inline) {
2     return badRequest(content, inline, StaticFileMimeTypes.fileMimeTypes());
3 }

```

Similarity Score: 50%

FIGURE 7: The third page of the functional similarity evaluation page.

FIGURE 8: The distribution of the programming languages used.

FIGURE 9: Histograms of the functional similarity scores derived (a) by our function and (b) by the developers.

Figure 10 illustrates a heatmap, which depicts the correlation between the similarity scores generated by our function and those provided by the participants. With the function's scores plotted along the horizontal axis and the user's scores plotted along the vertical axis, the color intensity of the heatmap indicates the frequency of occurrences. The high appearance of dark colors along the diagonal of the heatmap is evidence of agreement between the automated and human scores, highlighting a general agreement in the perceived functional similarity of code snippet pairs.

A significant observation from the heatmap is the concentration of values in the lower left quarter, indicating a bias toward lower similarity scores. This distribution pattern is attributed to the broad and general nature of the code snippets selected for this evaluation. Given the broad scope of the

CodeSearchNet corpus from which these snippets were drawn, finding pairs with more than 50% functional similarity is a challenging task. This tendency toward lower similarity scores is in line with expectations for a dataset covering a wide range of general programming tasks and supports the conclusion that both our function and the participants are mostly in agreement in their judgments of functional similarity, especially in the more common range of lower similarity percentages.

In order to provide a deeper statistical insight into the agreement between the similarity scores generated by our function and those determined by the participants, Table 6 presents several key metrics: *Cohen's kappa*, *weighted kappa*, *Kendall's tau*, *Pearson's r*, and *Spearman's rho*. These metrics confirm the effectiveness and robustness of our methodology, further supported by the observed visual agreement in heatmaps and

FIGURE 10: The correlation heatmap between the similarity scores derived from our function and the evaluation participants.

TABLE 6: The statistics of similarity between automated and human scores.

Metric	Value
Cohen's κ	0.12
Weighted κ	0.46
Kendall's τ	0.51 ($p = 0.002$)
Pearson's r	0.58 ($p = 0.004$)
Spearman's ρ	0.56 ($p = 0.004$)

histograms. This demonstrates the reliability of our system in assessing functional similarity across diverse programming contexts.

4.1.2. Real-World Application Potential. In this demonstration, we turn our focus to the practical efficiency of our system in a real-world setting, exploring its ability to return functionally similar snippets of code in response to user input. It serves as a critical test of our system to assess how well it performs under the complexities and variations inherent in real-world software development scenarios.

We selected a set of code snippets from the CodeSearchNet corpus that were not included in the initial set of code snippets used to train or fine-tune our system. Each of these selected snippets was then fed into our pipeline, triggering the system to search for and propose functionally similar alternatives from its database.

Code Snippet 3 depicts the first code snippet randomly selected from the CodeSearchNet corpus. The code snippet selected works in the context of OAuth2 authentication in Java, filtering an authentication object to determine if it is a standard OAuth2 authorized client and an instance of "OAuth2AuthenticationToken". It then casts the object to "OAuth2AuthenticationToken" and retrieves the "authorizedClientRegistrationId". This snippet serves as a test case to evaluate our system's ability to parse and match the functional

intent of specific OAuth2 authentication operations and to demonstrate its utility in suggesting relevant code changes or improvements.

The first suggestion made by our system for the input snippet, illustrated in **Code Snippet 4**, utilizes the *Mono* library and demonstrates an alternative approach to achieve the same functional operation as the original. This recommended snippet uses the programming capabilities of the *Mono* library to handle the authentication object more flexibly. It starts by creating a *Mono* instance of the authentication object and then performs a conditional check within a "flatMap" operation. This check mirrors the functionality of the original, determining whether the current authentication is the standard OAuth2 authorized client and an instance of "OAuth2AuthenticationToken". If these conditions are met, it casts the authentication to "OAuth2AuthenticationToken" and retrieves the "authorizedClientRegistrationId," encapsulating this value within a *Mono*. Conversely, if the conditions are not met, it returns an empty *Mono*. This suggestion illustrates the system's ability to not only recognize the functional objective of the snippet but also to suggest an alternative that conforms to modern programming patterns, potentially offering improved readability and compatibility within reactive Java applications.

The second alternative proposed by our system, depicted in **Code Snippet 5**, presents another slightly different variation using the *Mono* library that is aligned with the reactive programming paradigm, while closely following the functional objectives of the original snippet. This version uses the "Mono.justOrEmpty" constructor with the handle method, providing a streamlined approach to the reactive processing of the authentication object. Notably, this approach omits an explicit "else" block, implicitly handling cases where conditions are not met by not pushing any items into the sink, thus gracefully handling scenarios without matching criteria.

Code Snippet 6 displays the third recommendation snippet given by our methodology, which differs structurally from the original snippet, but remains within the same functional context, highlighting the system's capacity for diverse solution generation. This version starts by wrapping the "authenticationSource" in a "Mono <Authentication >" for a clearer and more modular approach. It then constructs a "Mono <String >" through a chain of reactive operations that reflect the logic of the original snippet, but with a different execution path. Overall, all recommendation snippets were relative to the "query" snippet both in terms of functionality, as well as in terms of libraries/entities used.

The second snippet in our evaluation scenario focuses on conditional logic for configuration settings, specifically around path handling and is depicted in **Code Snippet 7**. It outlines a series of checks and operations: if a path is not provided, it sets a default target; otherwise, it updates or initializes a mapping between a path and its target. This snippet is representative of typical configuration or mapping tasks in software development, making it an ideal candidate for assessing our system's ability to identify functionally similar code alternatives in such contexts.

Our system's top recommendation for the configuration handling snippet is shown in **Code Snippet 8** and uses Java's

```

return authentication
  .filter (t -> this.defaultOAuth2AuthorizedClient
    && t instanceof OAuth2AuthenticationToken)
  .cast (OAuth2AuthenticationToken.class)
  .map (OAuth2AuthenticationToken::getAuthorizedClientRegistrationId)
;

```

CODE SNIPPET 3: The first snippet of the real-world application comparison.

```

return Mono.justOrEmpty (authentication)
  .flatMap (auth -> {
    if (this.defaultOAuth2AuthorizedClient
      && auth instanceof OAuth2AuthenticationToken) {
      OAuth2AuthenticationToken oauthToken =
        (OAuth2AuthenticationToken) auth;
      return Mono.just (oauthToken
        .getAuthorizedClientRegistrationId());
    } else {
      return Mono.empty();
    }
  });

```

CODE SNIPPET 4: The first recommendation of our system for the first snippet of the comparison.

```

return Mono.justOrEmpty (authentication)
  .handle ((auth, sink) -> {
    if (this.isOAuth2Authentication
      && auth instanceof OAuth2AuthenticationToken) {
      OAuth2AuthenticationToken oauthToken =
        (OAuth2AuthenticationToken) auth;
      String registrationId = oauthToken
        .getAuthorizedClientRegistrationId();
      sink.next (registrationId);
    }
  });

```

CODE SNIPPET 5: The second recommendation of our system for the first snippet of the comparison.

```

Mono <Authentication > authenticationMono =
  Mono.justOrEmpty (authenticationSource);
Mono <String > clientRegistrationIdMono = authenticationMono
  .filterWhen (auth -> Mono
    .just (auth instanceof OAuth2AuthenticationToken
      && enableOAuth2Client))
  .cast (OAuth2AuthenticationToken.class)
  .map (oauth2Token -> oauth2Token
    .getAuthorizedClientRegistrationId());

```

CODE SNIPPET 6: The third recommendation of our system for the first snippet of the comparison.

```

if (path==null) {
  rootType=target;
  return this;
}
if (mappings==null) {
  mappings=new HashMap <> ();
}
mappings.put (Path.parse (path), target);

```

CODE SNIPPET 7: The second snippet of the real-world application comparison.

```

Optional.ofNullable (pathSpecifier)
  .ifPresentOrElse (
    path -> {
      if (this.typeMappings==null) {
        this.typeMappings=new HashMap <> ();
      }
      this.typeMappings.put (Path.convert (path), typeClass);
    },
    () -> this.defaultType = typeClass
  );

```

CODE SNIPPET 8: The first recommendation of our system for the second snippet of the comparison.

“Optional” class for a cleaner, more modern approach to conditional logic. By using “Optional.ofNullable” in combination with “ifPresentOrElse,” the suggestion elegantly handles the presence or absence of a path specifier, performing the necessary mapping or setting a default type accordingly. This recommendation not only matches the intent of the original snippet but also demonstrates the system’s ability to improve code quality by adopting current Java practices that emphasize readability.

To conclude this section, it is clear that our system is able to identify and provide functionally similar code snippets from the database that achieve the same goals using different approaches. The examples and their alternatives highlight the system’s ability not only to recognize functional equivalence but also to prioritize alternatives with high syntactic similarity. In particular, the first example shows that the system effectively narrows down the options to those with minimal syntactic differences from the original snippet. This aspect greatly simplifies the integration process for developers, allowing seamless adoption of suggested code enhancements.

4.1.3. Real-World Application Using Code Idioms. In the second real-world application scenario, we explore the practical applicability of our system when using the Code Idioms dataset as a source of code recommendations. This scenario tests our system’s ability to navigate real-world challenges using a dataset known for its high quality, reusable, and maintainable code snippets. Our goal is to present the effectiveness of our system in providing recommendations that not only meet the

functional requirements of the user-provided snippets but also incorporate superior software quality metrics.

To facilitate this hypothesis, we selected the idiomatic expressions from the Code Idioms dataset that were fed into our recommendation pipeline to check whether the system could identify and suggest these high-quality snippets as viable alternatives to the user’s original code. Our primary focus in this scenario is to carefully analyze each recommended idiom for its functional alignment with the user’s original snippet. This process involves a detailed inspection to verify that the recommended idioms not only adhere to the intended functionality but also improve the readability and maintainability of the code, characteristics inherent to idiomatic expressions.

In order to adapt our system for effective use of the Code Idioms dataset, we developed a new functional similarity algorithm. Due to the unique nature of code idioms, which are typically concise syntactic fragments with narrowly focused functionality, the original method of calculating similarity could not be applied. Our original approach, represented by **Equation (1)**, was designed to evaluate broad functional equivalence by comparing the intersection and union of action tags derived from two code snippets. However, this method proved less effective when applied to code idioms due to their specialized and limited scope, which often resulted in a sparse intersection of tags with the user’s more complex code snippets.

To address this challenge, we created a new similarity scoring equation to focus solely on the overlap of the idiom’s tags with those in the user’s snippet, without punishing the score for tags that are only present in the user’s code. The revised

```

FileInputStream fileInputStream = null;
Scanner scanner = null;
try {
fileInputStream = new FileInputStream ("example.txt");
scanner = new Scanner (fileInputStream, "UTF-8");
while (scanner.hasNextLine()) {
    System.out.println(scanner.nextLine());
}
} catch (Exception e) {
System.err.println ("Error: " + e.getMessage());
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 9: The first snippet of the code idioms comparison.

```

try {
$(object1).$(method1)();
} catch (Exception e) {
System.err.println ("Error: " + e.getMessage());
} finally {
if ($(object1) != null) {
    try {
        $(object1).close();
    } catch (Exception e) {
        System.err.println ("Close error: " + e.getMessage());
    }
}
}
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 10: The code idiom recommendation by our system.

formula now calculates the proportion of idiom tags that are also present in the user's snippet using the equation:

$$S = \frac{T_{\text{idiom}} \cap T_{\text{user}}}{T_{\text{idiom}}} \quad (7)$$

This adaptation allows our system to identify idioms that could potentially improve the quality of a user's code by incorporating well-defined, maintainable, and reusable elements, even if these idioms do not cover all the functionality of the original snippet. By focusing on the presence of idiom tags in the user's code, we can suggest snippets that contribute positively to code quality without necessarily replicating all existing functionality.

In our scenario, the user-provided code snippet, randomly selected from the CodeSearchNet corpus, performs file reading operations. This snippet, shown in **Code Snippet 9**, attempts to read from a text file. While the snippet includes basic error handling, it lacks proper resource management. This snippet serves as a sample input to our system, challenging it to recommend code improvements.

After running our code idioms similarity algorithm, the system returned a code idiom which, as the **Equation (7)** shows, does not encompass the full functionality of the user's snippet. However, it can significantly improve the quality of the user's code. The chosen code idiom, illustrated in **Code Snippet 10**, extends the user's code by incorporating robust error handling and resource management, while it adheres to high-quality standards.

Code Snippet 11 illustrates a modification of the initial user's snippet, in which the recommended code idiom by our system is manually incorporated to improve quality metrics.

This scenario demonstrates the effective integration of the Code Idioms dataset with our system and its ability to improve existing code by recommending snippets characterized by high quality, reusability, and maintainability. By modifying the functional similarity algorithm to focus on the idiomatic aspects of the code, our system successfully identifies idioms that complement the user's functionality while significantly improving the overall quality of the code. The integration of these idioms not only increases the robustness and readability of the code but also promotes best coding practices through structured error

```

FileInputStream fileInputStream = null;
Scanner scanner = null;

try {
fileInputStream = new FileInputStream ("example.txt");
scanner = new Scanner (fileInputStream, "UTF-8");
while (scanner.hasNextLine()) {
    System.out.println(scanner.nextLine());
}
} catch (Exception e) {
System.err.println ("Error reading file: " + e.getMessage());
} finally {
if (scanner != null) {
    try {
        scanner.close();
    } catch (Exception e) {
        System.err.println ("Scanner close error: "
            + e.getMessage());
    }
}
}
if (fileInputStream != null) {
    try {
        fileInputStream.close();
    } catch (Exception e) {
        System.err.println ("Input stream close error: "
            + e.getMessage());
    }
}
}
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 11: The user snippet after incorporating the recommended code idiom.

handling and resource management. This scenario highlights the practical utility of our recommendation system in real-world applications, proving its ability to improve software quality through meaningful, context-aware recommendations.

RQ1: *What are the key components of a quality-aware code-fixing system that can suggest functionally and/or syntactically similar snippets?*

Response to RQ1: *Our study clearly demonstrates that the proposed system contains all the necessary key components that are required to suggest functionally and syntactically similar snippets.*

4.2. Impact on Quality Metrics. In our second evaluation scenario, we shift our focus to a critical aspect of the impact of our system: its ability to produce specific quality improvements in code through its recommendations. This evaluation aims to test the initial hypothesis presented in our paper that the code recommendations generated by our system could help developers to improve certain quality attributes of their code, such as

maintainability, even with the understanding that these improvements may negatively affect other software quality attributes. This approach recognizes the general trade-offs that exist in software development, where optimizing the code for one quality attribute may require compromising for others.

To perform this evaluation, we provide our system with randomly selected snippets of code and analyzing the output. However, this time the focus goes beyond the functional and syntactic similarity of the recommended snippets. We conduct a comparative analysis of the quality metrics associated with both the original snippets provided by the user and the recommendations provided by our system. By quantitatively measuring the changes in quality metrics, such as complexity, readability, or maintainability, we aim to determine whether the system's suggestions are consistent with the goal of improving the targeted quality characteristics.

In our quality metrics evaluation, the randomly selected snippet, depicted in **Code Snippet 12**, involves checking an object for a specific method using reflection and performing error handling. The code searches for a method called "write" within "streamObj" and attempts to call it if found. Failure to

```

boolean result = true;

if (streamObj != null) {
    try {
        Method writeMethod = Arrays.stream(streamObj
            .getClass().getMethods())
            .filter(m -> m.getName().equals("write")
                && m.getParameterTypes().length == 3)
            .findFirst()
            .orElse(null);

        if (writeMethod != null) {
            writeMethod
                .invoke(streamObj, writeBuffer, 0, dataLength);
        } else {
            System.err.println("Write method not found.");
            result = false;
        }
    } catch (IllegalAccessException
        | InvocationTargetException e) {
        e.printStackTrace();
        result = false;
    }
} else {
    System.err.println("Stream object is null.");
    result = false;
}

return result ? dataLength : -2;

```

CODE SNIPPET 12: The randomly selected snippet of the quality metrics evaluation.

find the method, or an exception during the call, results in an error message and marks the operation as unsuccessful. The snippet concludes by determining the return value based on the success of the operation. This snippet serves as a basis for evaluating how our system's recommendations can affect key quality metrics and provides insight into the potential improvements in code quality from our suggested alternatives.

Building on the methods described in Section 3.2, we apply SourceMeter to the randomly selected code snippet to determine its software quality metrics. By obtaining these metrics, we set a benchmark against which the quality improvements suggested by our system's recommendations can be measured and evaluated. Table 7 depicts the software quality metrics derived for the snippet in **Code Snippet 12**. It should be noted that, from Table 4, only the metrics that refer to a single code snippet have been calculated, discarding metrics such as NII and NOI, which are calculated at the project level.

The first recommendation from our system is shown in **Code Snippet 13**. It closely mirrors the original code snippet,

TABLE 7: The calculated metrics for the randomly selected snippet.

Property	Metric	Value
Complexity	HCPL	156.24
	HDIF	15.75
	HEFF	6563.91
	HPL	80
	HPV	37
	HTRP	364.66
	HVOL	416.76
	MI	87.00
	McCC	5
	NL	3
Documentation	NLE	3
	CD	0
Size	CLOC	0
	LLOC	24
	LOC	27

```

if (mOpenStream==null || ! (mOpenStream instanceof DataOutput) )
return -1;

try
{
DataOutput output= (DataOutput) mOpenStream;
output.write (buf, 0, size);
return 1;
}
catch (IOException e)
{
log.error ("Got error: {}; {}", mOpenStream, e);
return -1;
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 13: The first recommendation provided by our system.

TABLE 8: The calculated metrics for the first recommendation of our system.

Property	Metric	Original Snippet	First Recommendation	
			Value	Improvement
Complexity	HCPL	156.24	109.24	30%
	HDIF	15.75	11.61	26%
	HEFF	6563.91	2511.84	62%
	HPL	80	45	44%
	HPV	37	28	24%
	HTRP	364.66	139.55	62%
	HVOL	416.76	216.33	48%
	MI	87.00	99.60	14%
	McCC	5	3	40%
	NL	3	2	33%
Documentation	NLE	3	2	33%
	CD	0	0	0%
Size	CLOC	0	0	0%
	LLOC	24	14	42%
	LOC	27	14	48%

Note: The bold values highlight the improved metric values in comparison to the initial snippet. These values indicate notable improvements in code quality metrics compared to the original snippet and are emphasized for ease of comparison.

both in functionality and syntax. This suggested snippet retains the essential logic of validating a stream object and performing an operation, showing our system's ability to provide alternatives that are not only functionally similar but also syntactically aligned. This syntactical similarity ensures that the recommendation can be easily adopted with minimal adjustments, highlighting our system's ability to offer practical code improvements.

After introducing the snippet recommended by our system, we analyze its quality metrics using SourceMeter and compare them with those of the original snippet. In Table 8, metrics that have been altered and positively affect the overall quality are highlighted in bold, while those that have a negative impact are highlighted in italic, providing a clear visual representation of how the recommendation affects different aspects of software quality.

The recommendation provided by our system significantly improves the complexity and size metrics of the original code snippet, indicating a more efficient and streamlined approach without compromising functionality. Notably, this alternative does not negatively impact the documentation and coupling metrics, maintaining a balance in aspects critical for long-term maintenance and scalability.

A second recommendation is given in **Code Snippet 14**, and the system suggests a snippet that is similar in functionality to both the original snippet and the first recommendation. However, it is slightly less syntactically similar and uses a more compact approach to error handling. Despite these minor differences, it maintains the core operation and logic, further highlighting the ability of our system to offer a range of practical alternatives tailored to the needs of developers.

```

if (stream != null) {
try {
    ((DataOutput)stream).write (buf, 0, size);
} catch (Exception ex) {
    System.out.println ("Failure writing to stream: " + ex);
    return 0;
}
return size;
} else {
    System.out.println ("Stream is not open or not suitable.");
return 0;
}

```

CODE SNIPPET 14: The second recommendation provided by our system.

After evaluating the second recommendation through SourceMeter, we observe its quality metrics in comparison to those of the original snippet. By presenting these metrics side-by-side with the original, we can assess the specific areas of improvement or change brought about by this recommendation. Table 9 depicts these metrics.

The quality metrics for the second recommendation reflect the positive impact seen in the first, particularly in the complexity and size metrics. Like the first recommendation, this alternative does not change the documentation and coupling metrics, maintaining consistency in these areas. However, it introduces differences in specific metrics; for example, it offers improvements in HCPL and Halstead Difficulty (HDIF), indicating potentially more efficient code. Conversely, metrics such as the maintainability index (MI) and McCC show less positive values compared to the original snippet, suggesting areas where this recommendation may introduce trade-offs. Metrics such as nesting level (NL) and LLOC remain unchanged, further highlighting the complex nature of software quality metrics.

This complex combination of metrics underscores the sensitive balance between different aspects of code quality and highlights the system's ability to provide custom recommendations. This enables developers to make informed choices between the alternatives provided, selecting the option that best meets their specific quality improvement goals and the unique needs of their projects. Thus, we can answer the second research question:

RQ2: *Does the proposed system effectively improve software quality metrics through its recommendations, thereby confirming the hypothesis that targeted code snippet replacements can enhance the overall quality attributes of software projects?*

Response to RQ2: *The results of the evaluation indicate that our system can successfully suggest functionally similar code snippets that have the potential to improve specific software quality metrics. This supports the initial hypothesis that appropriate selection and replacement of code snippets based on targeted quality attributes*

can lead to overall quality improvements in software projects.

4.3. Comparison With Large Language Models. The rapid advancement of LLMs has led to the creation of increasingly sophisticated tools capable of performing various tasks, including code generation and recommendation. Despite their growing popularity and impressive capabilities, the performance of LLMs in certain specialized applications, such as software quality improvement, remains an area of active research. To investigate whether an LLM could potentially replace our system, we designed an evaluation scenario comparing our approach with three prominent LLMs: an open-source model (Llama 3), a free model (Claude 3 Sonnet), and a paid model (GPT-4 o).

In this evaluation, we selected three axes for comparison:

- **Syntactic Correctness:** We assessed the syntactic correctness of the generated snippets by evaluating how many of the snippets recommended by each approach adhere to Java syntax.
- **Functional Similarity:** Using our previously validated functional similarity function, we measured the similarity of each recommended snippet to the user's original snippet, thereby assessing the practical utility of the recommendations.
- **Quality of Proposed Snippets:** We evaluated how effectively each approach improves the quality of the user's snippet, which is the primary goal of our system.

In addition, to fully exploit the capabilities of the LLMs, we incorporated a feedback loop into the evaluation scenario. After receiving the first recommendation from each LLM, we requested a second recommendation, emphasizing on syntactic correctness, functional similarity, and quality. This process was repeated three times, resulting in a total of four recommendations for each user snippet. The results of each evaluation axis are presented in the following subsections. For this scenario, we made use of 200 random snippets from our dataset, resulting in 200 recommendations in total from our methodology and 800 recommendations in total for each one of the three LLMs.

TABLE 9: The calculated metrics for the second recommendation of our system.

Property	Metric	Original Snippet	First Recommendation		Second Recommendation	
			Value	Improvement	Value	Improvement
Complexity	HCPL	156.24	109.24	30%	82.60	47%
	HDIF	15.75	11.61	26%	8.44	46%
	HEFF	6563.91	2511.84	62%	2213.72	66%
	HPL	80	45	44%	58	28%
	HPV	37	28	24%	23	38%
	HTRP	364.66	139.55	62%	122.98	66%
	HVOL	416.76	216.33	48%	262.37	37%
	MI	87.00	99.60	14%	94.29	8%
	McCC	5	3	40%	4	20%
	NL	3	2	33%	2	33%
Documentation	NLE	3	2	33%	2	33%
	CD	0	0	0%	0	0%
Size	CLOC	0	0	0%	0	0%
	LLOC	24	14	42%	14	42%
	LOC	27	14	48%	14	48%

Note: The bold values highlight the improved metric values in comparison to the initial snippet. These values indicate notable improvements in code quality metrics compared to the original snippet and are emphasized for ease of comparison.

TABLE 10: Syntactic Correctness of Recommended Snippets.

Model	Percentage of Syntactic Errors
Llama 3	25.50%
Claude 3 Sonnet	18.16%
GPT-4o	11.75%
Our Approach	0.00%

4.3.1. *Syntactic Correctness.* The syntactic correctness of the generated snippets was evaluated based on their adherence to Java syntax. The results are presented in Table 10.

Llama 3 exhibited the highest percentage of syntactic errors, which indicates that approximately one in four snippets generated by Llama 3 would require significant corrections before being usable, posing a potential burden for developers seeking reliable recommendations. While GPT-4o demonstrated the best performance of the LLMs, still one in 10 recommendations may be syntactically incorrect. In contrast, our approach, using a carefully curated dataset, maintained a perfect record with 0% syntactic errors. This result highlights the reliability of our system in providing syntactically correct code snippets, ensuring that all recommendations are immediately usable without further correction.

4.3.2. *Functional Similarity.* The functional similarity of the recommended snippets was evaluated using our validated functional similarity function. The average functional similarity scores are presented in Table 11.

Llama 3 showed a lower capability to generate functionally relevant snippets, which often deviate significantly from the intended functionality of the user's original snippet. Although Claude 3 Sonnet performed better, more than 70% of the recommendations may not match the user's functional

TABLE 11: Functional Similarity of Recommended Snippets.

Model	Average Functional Similarity
Llama 3	19.73%
Claude 3 Sonnet	28.12%
GPT-4o	30.38%
Our Approach	42.13%

requirements adequately. GPT-4o had the highest functional similarity among the LLM. Our approach showed the best performance, which highlights our system's superior ability to provide recommendations that closely match the original user snippets, significantly reducing the burden on developers to adapt the recommended code.

4.3.3. *Quality of Proposed Snippets.* The quality of the proposed snippets was assessed by comparing the percentage difference in various software quality metrics between the original user snippet and the recommended snippets. As mentioned in Section 4.2, only the metrics referring to individual code snippets have been calculated, discarding metrics affecting project wide components such as NII and NOI. The results are presented in Table 12.

The results in Table 12 indicate that LLMs do not incorporate documentation within the quality profile they use for snippet recommendations, neglecting the addition of comments within the code snippet, unless specifically told so. Similarly, in our approach, while our snippets dataset contains a documentation field that describes the snippet's use and could be used to increase the documentation metrics, we chose not to leverage it. However, in principle, our approach demonstrated the smallest impact on documentation, meaning that it still preserves some comments.

TABLE 12: The percentage difference per metric between the original user snippet and the recommended snippet for each model.

Property	Metric	Llama 3	Claude 3 Sonnet	GPT-4o	Our Approach
Complexity	HCPL	-40.79%	+10.65%	-12.59%	-45.19%
	HDIF	-46.74%	-1.80%	-13.37%	-47.32%
	HEFF	-50.39%	+14.09%	-8.26%	-62.35%
	HPL	-42.73%	-0.61%	-18.27%	-32.51%
	HPV	-37.56%	-1.41%	-12.89%	-37.49%
	HTRP	-50.39%	+14.09%	-8.26%	-58.23%
	HVOL	-45.84%	+12.10%	-18.07%	-37.14%
	MI	+17.12%	+10.73%	+8.51%	+12.35%
	McCC	-27.32%	+2.27%	-15.24%	-28.32%
	NL	-64.99%	-50.80%	-51.71%	-56.23%
Documentation	NLE	-66.17%	-48.14%	-50.36%	-57.32%
	CD	-56.73%	-92.96%	-77.25%	-35.46%
Size	CLOC	-87.59%	-93.22%	-84.34%	-37.43%
	LLOC	-37.12%	-4.24%	-5.14%	-39.26%
	LOC	-38.32%	-2.21%	-0.32%	-40.23%

Note: The bold and italic values represent the improvement (in bold) or the setback (in italic) of the metric values compared to the original user snippet, across the models evaluated. These values highlight the relative performance of each model.

Llama 3 showed the best performance among the LLMs in improving complexity and size metrics. GPT-4o also had a positive impact on complexity and size metrics, but the improvements were less significant compared to Llama 3. Claude 3 Sonnet displayed mixed results. It showed minor improvements in some complexity metrics, but also had negative impacts on others. These results suggest that Claude 3 Sonnet's recommendations are less consistent in enhancing code quality and may sometimes decrease it. Our approach produced the best overall results. It significantly improved complexity metrics and, also, produced a significant reduction in size metrics. Despite not focusing on documentation, the impact of our system was minimal compared to the LLMs, indicating a better preservation of code comments.

These results confirm the complex nature of software quality metrics. While LLMs such as Llama 3 showed promising improvements in some metrics, our approach consistently delivered better results. Our system's tailored, domain-specific methodology ensures comprehensive improvements in code quality, outperforming the latest LLMs.

In terms of quality, which is the primary focus of our system, our approach, while generally superior, is only comparable to Llama 3. However, while Llama 3 produces very good results in terms of quality metrics, it regularly fails to produce syntactically correct code. Furthermore, when Llama 3 does generate syntactically correct code, the recommended snippets often differ significantly from the original in terms of functionality, increasing the burden on developers to adapt these suggestions. The comprehensive performance of our approach demonstrates the effectiveness of our customized, domain-specific solution in providing high quality, functionally relevant and syntactically correct code recommendations, thereby reducing developer workload and improving the overall software development process. These results allow us to respond to the third research question:

RQ3: *Given the advances and capabilities of large language models (LLMs) in understanding and generating code, could an LLM effectively replace the proposed system by performing the same tasks of identifying functionally similar code snippets and recommending alternatives with better quality metrics?*

Response to RQ3: *Our study shows that while large language models (LLMs) have made significant progress in understanding and generating code, they are not yet able to fully replace our proposed system. LLMs such as Llama 3, Claude 3 Sonnet and GPT-4o struggle with various aspects that are crucial for effective code recommendations. Our system outperforms these LLMs in all evaluation criteria. Therefore, our customized, domain-specific solution remains essential for developers seeking reliable, high-quality code recommendations.*

5. Conclusions and Future Work

In this study, we presented a system designed to suggest alternative code snippets to developers based on both functional and syntactic similarities. The evaluation of our system in the context of software quality improvement has validated its effectiveness in providing actionable code alternatives that align with desired quality metric improvements. Through a systematic approach to functional and syntactic similarity analysis, coupled with a comprehensive evaluation against established quality metrics, our study has demonstrated the system's potential to significantly assist developers in improving the quality of their software. By facilitating a detailed understanding of the complex trade-offs associated with software quality,

the system provides a valuable tool for tackling these challenges, enabling developers to achieve a more balanced and quality-focused codebase.

As observed in Table 9, the system prioritizes recommendations based on their potential to improve quality metrics while maintaining functional and syntactic similarity to the original snippet. While the selection of multiple recommendations can enhance overall quality metrics, the system is designed to ensure that the most impactful recommendations are presented first. Developers are advised to start with the top-ranked recommendations, as these are optimized for balancing quality improvement with minimal changes. Beyond the initial suggestions, additional recommendations may have less of an impact, as they are less aligned with the user's original code.

In addition, our comparative analysis with LLMs such as Llama 3, Claude 3 Sonnet, and GPT-4o has highlighted the strengths and limitations of these advanced models in the context of code recommendation. While LLMs show promise in generating code snippets, they often fall short in terms of syntactic correctness and functional similarity, which are crucial for practical utility. Our system consistently outperformed these models on all evaluation axes, highlighting the importance of specialized, domain-specific solutions in software development.

Our system has some limitations tied to its dependency on the existing dataset and reliance on predefined quality metrics. The dataset, currently optimized for common coding practices, may not adequately cover highly specialized or domain-specific code, such as embedded systems. Similarly, the predefined quality metrics focus on attributes like maintainability and readability, which may not fully capture the requirements of specialized domains, such as real-time performance.

However, these limitations can be mitigated as the system evolves. The dataset has the potential to grow dynamically through user feedback and expanded examples, gradually broadening its applicability to more complex and specialized scenarios. Future work will also focus on extending the quality model to incorporate domain-specific metrics, ensuring the system can address a wider variety of programming tasks.

Future work may involve, also, a detailed user experience and usability study, which will refine the system's interface and functionality, ensuring that it fits seamlessly into developers workflows. In addition, embedding our recommendation engine into popular integrated development environments (IDEs) to bring quality improvement suggestions directly into the software development process, providing real-time guidance and support.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in the work presented have been collected from our previous works and the CodeSearchNet corpus.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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Endnotes

¹<https://sourcemeeter.com/>

²<https://www.nltk.org/>

³<https://spacy.io/universe/project/spacy-universal-sentence-encoder>

⁴<https://functional-similarity-evaluation.netlify.app/>

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